

HIGHLY ACCURATE IRRADIATION AND TEMPERATURE CONTROL FOR NEXT-GENERATION PV MODULE CHARACTERISATION

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ABSTRACT: In this paper, an advanced module solar simulator based on LEDs as irradiation sources is described, and its performance concerning control of irradiation and temperature is measured. The spectral match to the standard AM1.5G spectrum is outstanding between 400 nm-1100 nm, with a maximum deviation in the spectral intervals <2%, where <25% is required for class A simulators, according to the IEC standard. The irradiance non-uniformity across a 1.6 m x 1 m area is currently 2.1%, which is just above the 2% limit for class A, but this can be improved by adjusting the LED beam directions slightly. The long-term irradiance instability is 0.09%, which is well below the 2% limit of class A. Since the high efficiency modules of today can still produce significant current below 400 nm and above 1100 nm, the updated IEC standard (expected by 2020) will extend the total spectral range to 300 nm-1200 nm for the new class A+. Introducing other LED types in future upgrades will enable the spectrum to be closely matching the AM1.5G spectrum also below 350 nm and above 1100 nm. Finally, actual module measurements at different temperature/irradiance combinations are presented to demonstrate the capabilities of the simulator.

Keywords: Solar simulator, LED, characterisation

1 INTRODUCTION

To measure the electrical properties of a photovoltaic (PV) module at Standard Test Conditions (STC), traditional solar simulators use a xenon flash lamp as the light source to simulate the AM1.5G solar spectrum. An infrared filter is applied to reduce the height of the xenon emission peaks at long wavelengths and achieve a better match to the AM1.5G spectrum. A comparison between a typical filtered xenon flash lamp spectrum and the AM1.5G spectrum is given in Figure 1. It is clear that this way of spectral simulation is not ideal, but for many years this was the way to do it.

Figure 1: Spectrum for xenon flash lamp with filter (red curve) compared to the AM1.5G spectrum. The curves are quite close for visible light, but not any more above 800 nm.

Another issue with xenon flash lamps is, that the short duration of the flash (typically well below 100 ms) is not optimal. It is generally too short to measure high efficiency modules correctly due to capacitive effects [1], and it limits the possibility for noise reduction by signal integration. Finally, obtaining accurate *I-V* measurements at different intensities is also difficult when using a flash lamp since it must be done while the irradiance is decreasing very quickly.

For cell simulators these issues can be avoided by using a xenon lamp for continuous operation, but for

module simulators this is not practical. As a high and uniform irradiance is required across an area of up to 2 m², a lamp power in the range of tens of kW would be required. So instead, a flash lamp producing a very high peak irradiance is placed at a large distance (4-5 m) from the module for good uniformity. An additional advantage of this approach is that a flash has almost no influence on module temperature during the *I-V* measurement.

To address the limitations of a short flash, its duration has been increased by some manufacturers up to 100 ms. In addition, bidirectional *I-V* sweeping can be applied to correct for possible capacitive effects. Nevertheless, these adaptations do not solve the large spectral deviation.

As LEDs with ever-increasing power became available over the last decade, some solar simulator manufacturers have replaced the xenon lamp by a large number of LEDs (of different spectral types). In this way, there is more flexibility to simulate a desired spectrum by adjusting the intensities of the different LED types. In addition to this, the LEDs can easily be used for longer flash duration and to vary the irradiance. Another advantage is that the lifetime of LEDs is longer than for xenon lamps, that have to be replaced regularly.

In 2018, a special new LED simulator from the company Wavelabs has been installed at imec. This new model Sinus-2100p irradiates the solar module with 16320 individual LEDs, distributed over 60 LED-boxes that are mounted in a parabolic wall, and that is placed at a distance of ~5 meters from the module. This simulator can control module temperature and can also provide additional LED illumination from the back side for bifacial modules. Currently, only a few Sinus-2100p setups have been installed worldwide. The extra option of the temperature-controlled chamber with additional back side illumination has been only installed at imec, so as a complete system it is unique in the world.

A drawing of it and some pictures of the tool operated with different spectral distributions are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Wavelabs Sinus 2100p with temperature-controlled chamber concept (left), implementation with spectral variation in irradiation (right)

Since imec is also working on accurate energy yield modelling, it is important to have a simulator that enables the I - V measurement for a range of temperature/irradiance combinations. Different temperature/irradiance combinations are also needed when testing modules for the energy rating standard IEC 61853 [2].

In this work, first the evolution of solar simulation and standards will be given as an important background, followed by a detailed description of the Sinus-2100p tool. It will be explained how accurate control is obtained over irradiation and temperature, and afterwards the actually measured properties of the tool will be given. These results will be critically discussed and finally some I - V measurements obtained at different conditions will be presented.

2 EVOLUTION OF SOLAR SIMULATION

Concerning the spectrum quality of the traditional xenon lamp irradiation, Figure 1 showed that this still resulted in relatively large spectral errors in the infrared. For this historic reason, the spectral requirements in the standard IEC 60904-9 [2] about solar simulator irradiation quality have been relatively weak (see Table I, in which also the requirements for uniformity and temporal instability of the irradiance E are included). Since simulators with higher irradiation accuracy became available over the last decade, it was felt that a new top-class A+ had to be introduced. This has been done by TUV Rheinland some years ago, and this class has now also been included in the draft version of IEC60904-9 edition 3 (expected to be finished by July 2020).

Table I: Classification of solar simulator quality, designated by class A, B, C as defined in IEC 60904-9 Ed. 2. Class A+ is in the draft of the upcoming edition 3.

Classification	Spectral Match (per wavelength interval)	Spatial Non-Uniformity	Long Term Instability
Class A+	0.875–1.125	1%	1%
Class A	0.75–1.25	2%	2%
Class B	0.6–1.4	5%	5%
Class C	0.4–2.0	10%	10%

So even for a spectral class A simulator, absolute deviations of the integrated irradiance up to 25% are

allowed (over each of 6 wavelength intervals). It should be noted that the limit values for non-uniformity and instability in Table I are to be compared with the outcome of $(E_{max}-E_{min})/(E_{max}+E_{min})$. Since the denominator is 2 times the average, this means that each allowed limit value x should be interpreted as allowing a range of $\pm x\%$.

Next to the evolution in solar simulation, there has been also an evolution in the efficiency of cells and modules over the last decades. This means that the original spectral requirements for solar simulation are not adequate anymore. In edition 2, all wavelengths below 400 nm and above 1100 nm are not taken into account for spectral classification. In the past, this range limitation was fine, since cells and modules had almost negligible output outside the 400 nm-1100 nm range. Nowadays, the cells and modules can also convert irradiation outside this range into electric current. For this reason, the whole range of 300 nm-1200 nm is now taken into account in the draft of IEC 60409-9 edition 3 for the new class A+.

In the following, the class A+ will not yet be taken into account, since it is not included in the current standard.

3 DESCRIPTION SINUS-2100P AT IMEC

As was shown in Figure 2, the Sinus 2100p system consists of 2 main parts: a front light source containing the LEDs, and a temperature-controlled chamber at a few meters distance from the light source.

The front light source consists of 60 identical LED boxes mounted in a metal frame of parabolic shape. Each LED box contains 18 different LED types which enables a close match of the total spectrum to the AM1.5G spectrum. In Figure 3, the spectra of the individual LED types are shown, together with the AM1.5G spectrum.

Figure 3: Spectra for the 18 available LED types

Since the LEDs are water cooled, it is possible to run the LEDs not only in flash mode, but even in continuous mode. In the following, important features of the tool will be described.

3.1 In-situ irradiation spectrum control

A spectrometer is part of the setup, it measures the actual spectrum for every I - V measurement next to the module. During the first part of every flash (before the I - V tracing starts) the spectrum is adjusted through a feedback loop with the LED boxes to obtain an optimal spectrum.

In Figure 4, the spectrum of the LED simulator and the AM1.5G spectrum are shown like it is displayed on the screen of the setup for each measurement. The irradiance deviations per interval are also indicated, the largest one being only 1.69 %.

Figure 4: Spectrum of the Wavelabs simulator (orange) compared to AM1.5G (black), and the integrated irradiance differences per wavelength interval

3.2 Spectral range

The current spectral range of the LED illumination is 350 nm-1100 nm. So in the UV range the spectrum stops at 350 nm, although the AM1.5G spectrum does not stop yet. The reason for this is that the deeper UV LEDs were not yet efficient enough to be applied in the setup. For the current version of the tool wavelengths above 1100 nm are missing, while high efficiency silicon cells and modules can still produce current for wavelengths up to 1200 nm. With the evolution of LED technology both UV and extended IR LEDs could be added.

One particularly interesting feature is the possibility to operate the LED types individually, so that an estimated EQE curve with 18 data points can be constructed, see references [3,4,5].

3.3 Adjustable irradiance

In addition to the spectrum measurement, the irradiance of the flash is also monitored during the flash, and a correction for the very small irradiance variations can be applied. The irradiance can be calibrated with a calibration module, and the irradiance can be set from 10%-125% of one sun.

3.4 Temperature control

In the temperature-controlled chamber, the module can be kept at any temperature between 10 °C and 80 °C. The temperature is regulated by blowing heated/cooled air from the bottom side into the chamber and remove it from the top side. The temperature of the module is measured with 9 sensors of the Pt1000 type, that can be fixed onto the module back surface using tape. The temperature uniformity inside the chamber can be adjusted by bending fixed metal valves that are distributed along the top and bottom air inlet/outlet of the chamber to a more open or closed position. The chamber is closed during temperature regulation, it opens a shutter during the measurement but only for a few seconds to keep the module temperature stable.

3.5 Module sizes and shapes

Modules from 20 cm x 20 cm up to 100 cm x 200 cm can be mounted, with the possibility to measure curved modules as well.

3.6 I-V curve tracing

Modules with open circuit voltages from 0.5 V up to 200 V can be measured, so both c-Si and thin film modules. The maximum current is 20 A, enough for all modules, also bifacial ones. The number of points per

curve can be adjusted (at maximum a few thousand), although the software limits the number of points when a short flash duration has been selected. By using a longer flash duration, the noise in the curve can be reduced, typically a value of 500 ms-1000 ms is used.

3.7 Bifacial measurements

For the measurement of bifacial modules with illumination from both sides, it is possible to use LED illumination from the back side as well. The spectral class and uniformity of this illumination are less than for the front side, however.

To simulate a measurement with illumination from both sides, the standard for bifacial measurements IEC 60904-1-2 [2] also describes a method to increase the front side illumination by either 100 W/m² or 200 W/m², multiplied by the bifaciality coefficient. To be more precise, it is the minimum of the bifaciality coefficients for short circuit current I_{sc} and power at the maximum power point P_{mpp} .

Since the front side irradiance of this tool can be increased up to 1250 W/m², also these bifacial measurements can be performed on the system.

For this type of bifacial I-V measurements, it is important to minimise the reflection of any material behind the module. For this reason, the rear shutter that covers the rear side LEDs when they are not in use, is covered with black (insulation) material. This material has a more or less constant total reflection of only 5% over the wavelength range 400-1100 nm. In the bifacial standard, a maximum rear side irradiance of 3 W/m² is allowed.

3.8 Electroluminescence (EL) imaging

Another feature of the tool is high resolution EL imaging (1 pixel corresponding to 95 μm x 95 μm). The module is inspected using a scanning camera, followed by stitching the EL images together afterwards in the software.

4 EVALUATING ACCURACY OF THE TOOL

4.1 Spectral accuracy

As has been shown in Figure 4, the maximum spectral deviation for all wavelength intervals of the current IEC standard in a typical measurement at 1000 W/m² was 1.69%. The deviation can vary a bit from flash to flash and as a function of irradiance, but the deviation typically stays well below 5%. Anyway, it is clearly below the class A requirement of 25%.

However, it should be mentioned that the deviations have been only reported for the wavelength intervals of the current edition of the IEC standard that do not go below 400 nm and above 1100 nm. Since there is no LED irradiation between 1100 nm-1200 nm and between 300 nm-350 nm, the maximum deviation would be higher (~15%) for the future edition of the standard when the intervals will be distributed over the 300-1200 nm range for the new class A+. Wavelabs is working on a solution for this issue, so that the spectrum of the tool can be upgraded to a wider one in the future.

4.2 Spatial non-uniformity of the irradiance

The spatial uniformity of the irradiance has been checked by measuring the I_{sc} of a single cell module (cell size 156 mm x 156 mm), as recommended in IEC 60409-9. The designated test area was that of a 60-cell module

(cell size 156 mm x 156 mm), and the irradiance was determined at each cell location, covering the whole test area. In Figure 5, the spatial distribution of the irradiance is shown, given as the percentual deviation from $(E_{\max} - E_{\min})/2$.

Figure 5: Spatial non-uniformity of the irradiance (in % deviation of $(E_{\max} - E_{\min})/2$). Results have been measured in a 6 x 10 matrix on a 60 cells-module, using a mini-module with 156 mm x 156 mm cell as a detector.

From these measurements, the current value for the spatial non-uniformity over the 1.6 m x 1 m area is determined to be 2.1%, so just above the limit for class A. However, since the beam direction of each LED-box is adjustable, it should not be difficult to reduce this value below 2%.

4.3 Long term temporal instability

The IEC standard distinguishes between short-term instability (STI) and long-term instability (LTI) of the irradiance. The STI specifies the change of irradiance between measurement of irradiance and the measurement of voltage or current. However, for the Wavelabs tool, current, voltage and irradiance are measured simultaneously, so the STI cannot be determined (can be considered zero).

The LTI specifies the change in irradiance during an I - V measurement, which is the total duration of the flash (after ~80 ms of stabilisation time) in the case of the Wavelabs system. The irradiance is also measured for every flash using a photosensor that is included as extra sensor in the spectrometer of the tool.

For a typical flash, the irradiance variations as a function of time are shown in Figure 6. In this graph, the plotted values are the relative deviations from the average irradiance.

Figure 6: Relative deviations from average irradiance as a function of time during a flash

From this graph, it is clear that the LTI is well below the limit of 2% for the class A, in fact it is 0.09%.

4.4 Temperature non-uniformity across 60-cell module

For the evaluation of temperature uniformity, the 9 Pt1000 sensors of the setup were fixed to a 60-cell module in a 3 x 3 matrix. After optimisation of the temperature uniformity (using the valve bending method mentioned in the previous section), it was found that the temperature variations across the module stayed within $\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ of the set temperature at the highest set value of 80°C .

4.5 Rear side irradiance for bifacial measurements

As mentioned in the tool description, the rear side irradiance should not exceed 3 W/m^2 when bifacial modules are characterised using front side irradiation only. This has been investigated for our tool, mounting a mini module containing a 156 mm x 156 mm cell at the rear side of a bifacial module, while irradiating from the front side only. An aperture was placed around the bifacial module to reduce the amount of back-reflected irradiation as much as possible. Measuring at 4 different locations, it was found that the irradiance varied from 2-3 W/m^2 , meeting the requirement of the standard IEC 60904-1-2 standard.

5 APPLICATION EXAMPLES

As mentioned before, the tool has been designed to measure I - V curves at different combinations of temperature and irradiance. These measurements have been done at 5 temperatures in the range of 25°C - 70°C , while varying the irradiance between 0.1 and 1.2 suns for each temperature. The resulting I - V curves for a 60-cells bifacial glass-glass module are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: I - V curves measured at different temperature/irradiance combinations for a 60-cell bifacial glass-glass module.

These graphs can be used to determine a module's $I(V)$ equation as a function of irradiance and temperature, as is needed for energy yield calculations.

Also temperature coefficients for the different curve parameters can be deduced from curves shown in Figure 7. As an example, P_{mpp} as a function of temperature has been determined using the I - V curves measured at 1 sun. The data points are plotted in Figure 8, as well as a linear fit to these points and the corresponding thermal coefficient TC for P_{mpp} .

Figure 8: Curve of P_{mpp} as a function of temperature, including linear fit and calculated temperature coefficient for P_{mpp} .

6 CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

In this paper, it has been demonstrated how I - V measurements with accurate irradiation and temperature control can be obtained with the Wavelabs 2100p LED-based solar simulator that has been installed at imec.

It was found that the spectral match to AM1.5G was outstanding across the 400 nm-1100 nm range, with a largest spectral deviation of only 1.69 %, while <25% is required for class A. However, it should be mentioned that this very good result will be not enough to meet the requirement for the new class A+ in the future edition of the IEC standard. This is because the maximum irradiance deviation from AM1.5G of 12.5% will be evaluated over intervals covering a wider range, from 300 nm-1200 nm. Below 350 nm and above 1100 nm the current LEDs do not emit at all, so there is still improvement possible. Wavelabs is currently developing such an upgrade using other LED types.

The irradiance non-uniformity was found to be 2.1%, which is just above the 2% limit for class A. However, it should not be too difficult to get below the limit by optimisation of the LED-box beam directions. This is planned for later this year, using a special module that can measure the non-uniformity in a single flash.

The long-term temporal instability of the irradiance is only around 0.09%, which is way below the 2% required for the A class.

Combining these properties with a temperature range of 10 °C-80 °C and a temperature non-uniformity of ± 2 °C, this is tool is ideal to obtain the accurate I - V curves needed for accurate energy yield modelling.

The tool can be used for a wide variety of modules, including thin film, curved surfaces, and bifacial ones. Some measurements at different temperature/irradiance combinations have been presented and temperature coefficients calculated.

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